

TRANSLATION STRATEGY AS A BASIC CONCEPT OF TRANSLATING SUBTITLES

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Annotation. *The film industry and everything connected with it invariably arouses interest and controversy among specialists in various fields, as well as among ordinary spectators. In recent decades, due to the active development of the field communications, the Internet and various social networks, interest in film production increased several times. And since the main films are released in English, interest has grown in such a phenomenon as subtitles for movies and series.*

Key words: *caption, language, film, broadcast time, characters, comments, film industry, frame, subtitle.*

In modern translation studies to describe the translation process the phrase "translation strategy" is widely used. It can meet both in scientific and educational literature, as well as in various kinds of normative documents - in curricula, plans, examination tickets, etc.

Shlepnev D. N. argues that "the phrase "translation strategy" at first glance, it carries a certain terminology, and the concept denoted by it - to belong to the fundamental concepts of translation studies. However, when trying to find out what exactly science about translation understands the translation strategy and how much use this phrase deepens our knowledge of reality (in this case of the translation process), a far from unambiguous picture is revealed" [4, 161].

In our study, we found that the definition "translation strategy" is not in the "Explanatory Translation Dictionary" Nelyubina L. L., the most complete special to date translation reference manual, "which contains 2028 vocabulary articles extracted

from 224 sources” Meanwhile, the phrase "translation strategy" was widely used, in particular, Schweitzer A. D., Komissarov V. N. and continue to use them followers[3].

However, the term "translation strategy" can be found in several options. So, together with the "translation strategy" we can meet "translator strategy", "translation strategy", "translation tactics" and See also "the strategy of the translator's behavior in the process of translation." All these phrases are used as semantic variants.

It is worth noting that not only different, but sometimes even the same Researchers put different meanings into this phrase. From one side, it is used in the broadest sense, in the sense of "as translate correctly. Often in this case one speaks of a general "strategy translation".

Kryukov N. A. in the textbook "Theory of Translation" talks about the plan activities that the translator develops, but at the same time also uses the phrase "translation strategy", and also, as variant, the phrase "strategic line" [19. 48]. However, not clarifies the description of any specific actions to perform task, since the opinion prevails that “the strategy translation” can and should be developed and then implemented by everyone translator yourself.

Komisarov V. N. “A translation strategy is understood as potentially conscious plans of the translator, which are aimed at solving specific translation problems within a specific translation situation and are called upon to achieve a certain goal, which is due to a certain translation task” [3, p. 92-93]. Also Komisarov V.N. States that in literary translation, for example, “the strategic task is to transfer of the artistic and aesthetic function of the original” [3, p. 84].

Komissarov V. N. in his work "Modern Translation Studies" defines strategy as “a kind of translational thinking that underlies the translator's actions" [3, p. 356], and distinguishes three groups principles for implementing a "translation strategy": some initial installations; choosing a common course of action; character choice and sequence of actions in the translation process.

The first who spoke about the concept of "translation strategy" is German linguist, professor of applied linguistics H. Krings. He proposed to consider as this concept a

potential plan actions of an interpreter who acts in the process of solving certain translation tasks. At the same time, H. Krings distinguished between the concepts of macro- and microstrategies. Macrostrategy implies methods of solving certain tasks, and microstrategy is the solution of a single task [2].

Sdobnikov V.V. in his work "In search of a strategy" claims that "such a concept as a translation strategy implies the essence and the order of actions of the translator in the process of working with a specific text. In this situation, it is also appropriate to use the concept of "action translator" [1, p. 38].

Based on the work of Alekseeva I.S., referring to the works H. Krings, "translation strategy" can be represented as an algorithm translator's actions. This strategy aims to create product, which in this case is the translated text.

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